

Understanding and harnessing the potential of layered hybrid perovskite-based absorbers

Meenakshi Pegu^{1†}, Muhammed P. U. Haris^{1†}, Samrana Kazim^{1,2}, Shahzada Ahmad^{1,2*}

¹BCMaterials, Basque Center for Materials, Applications and Nanostructures,
UPV/EHU Science Park, 48940 Leioa, Spain

Tel: +34 946128811 Email: shahzada.ahmad@bcmaterials.net

²IKERBASQUE, Basque Foundation for Science, Bilbao, 48009, Spain

†Equal contribution

Abstract:

Hybrid perovskite-based absorbers are promising materials for the fabrication of next-generation thin film photovoltaics, owing to their cost effectiveness and low amount of materials usage. Three-dimensional (3D) perovskite analogues have shown outstanding potential in terms of power conversion efficiency; however, the concern about its long-term stability obstructs its co-industrial endeavour. One such approach is the development and employment of lower dimensional, i.e. layered perovskite structures that aims to achieve an excellent stability along with competitive photovoltaic performance. Layered perovskite absorbers also provide a credible pathway of tuning the optoelectronic properties by selective spacer groups. We highlight the use of layered perovskite bases absorbers in the photovoltaics how the structure, optoelectronics, charge carrier dynamics and their influence on the photovoltaic properties.

Keywords: Thin film Solar cells; perovskite solar cells; layered perovskites; Ruddlesden-Popper phase; Dion Jacobson perovskites; layered/3D perovskites, lead free perovskites

1. Introduction:

Hybrid organic-inorganic halide perovskites emerged as the competitive candidate for perovskite solar cells (PSCs) fabrication, owing to their inexpensive, solution processed route and exceptional photovoltaic (PV) properties stemmed from high absorption coefficients, long charge carrier diffusion length, improved structural and compositional flexibility.[1-5] The current decade has witnessed landmark research progress of perovskites for solar energy conversion in optoelectronics devices and being discussed in the PV industries.[6] At the time of writing of this report, several industrial companies are projecting the production of PSCs in next 1-2 years.[7-8] The power conversion efficiency (PCE) has reached extraordinarily to 25.5% for a single junction PSCs, and close to 30% in tandem configuration.[9] In a seminal work, three dimensional perovskite structure was developed by Weber et al in 1978 and the next landmark result was reported by Mitzi and co-workers in 1990 its distinctive optoelectronic properties.[10-11] Firstly, the hybrid halide perovskite as the light harvester was used in dye-sensitized solar cell (DSSCs) by Miyasaka and co-workers in the year 2009.[12] The PCE reported was 3.8% and in 2012, Park et al. developed the usage of solid-state hole transporting material (HTM) Spiro-OMeTAD in $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ and reported a PCE of 9.7%, this was followed by another report by Snaith et al. with a PCE of 10%.[2, 13] Different studies led to further optimization of results and improved device performances was reported.[14-18] Research efforts have been delineated on optimising the different layers including the perovskite absorber composition, hole transport layers (HTLs) {such as Spiro-OMeTAD, poly(triarylamine) (PTAA), poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene)-poly(styrene sulfonate) (PEDOT:PSS)}[19], electron transporting layer, (ETLs) {such as meso- TiO_2 , SnO_2 , [6,6]-Phenyl C₆₁butyric acid methyl ester (PCBM)} and selective contacts (Au, Ag, Cu) depending upon the architecture of the devices.[20-22] Significant focuses were also laid on the long-term stability for commercial exploitation of PSCs by passivating the trap defects, device encapsulation and interface modification.[23] To withstand the stability of the PSCs, various compositional engineering has been imposed on the three dimensional (3D) perovskite such as use of ionic liquids, moisture impermeable layers, or use of ETLs or HTLs functionalized with distinct organic groups.[24-25] Another attractive strategy involves the reduction of dimensionality to produce lower dimensional perovskites (layered perovskites), quasi layered, quasi-3D perovskites that can improve

the stability of PSCs.[26-31] This can be formed by incorporating a large bulky organic spacer cation that does not fit in the octahedral network of the perovskite structure (Fig. 1). The incorporation of the layered perovskite (aptly referred in the literature also as 2D perovskites) relaxes the limitations implied by the Goldschmidt tolerance factor and due to its robustness hinders the internal ionic motion. Additionally, the hydrophobic character induced by the larger organic 2D cations allows to improve the stability by withstanding the surface water absorption.[32-35] However, their large optical band gap and lower charge carrier transport typically limits their choice as an ideal absorber for solar cell fabrication. An alternative approach of employing a bilayer structure, i.e., a layered perovskite atop of 3D perovskite absorber or quasi 3D perovskites, to boost the stability and performance of the PSCs.[36]

In this review, we discuss the structural, optoelectrical and advancement in the field of layered perovskites for various optoelectronic applications. We highlight the structural, optical, charge carrier dynamics, optoelectronic properties and PV performances of the layered/3D perovskite bilayer. Some of the key challenges that needs to be addressed and a brief overview for future directions of the hybrid lower directional perovskites is presented.

Fig.1 Schematic representation of layered and 3D perovskite structures (layered, $n = 1-4$; 3D $n = \infty$)

2. Structural Characterization

The connectivity of metal halide octahedra constitute the dimensionality of metal halide perovskites. The halide perovskites are represented by ABX_3 , where A is a monovalent cation (MA^+ , FA^+ or Cs^+ etc) and B is the divalent metal cation (Pb^{2+} , Sn^{2+} and Ge^{2+} etc) and X is a monovalent halide (Br^- , Cl^- and I^-). 3D perovskites are characterized by the network of corner shared metal halide octahedra extended in all the 3 directions and the A type cations are occupied at the voids created by the interconnected octahedra where A, B and X can be one or multiple elements.[37] The stability as well as distortion of 3D perovskite structures can be predicted by means of geometric calculations such as Goldschmidt tolerance factor (t) and octahedral factor (m).

$$t = \frac{r_A + r_X}{\sqrt{2}(r_B + r_X)}$$
$$\mu = r_B/r_X$$

where, r_A , r_B and r_X indicate the ionic radii of A, B and X ions respectively. $0.8 < t \leq 1$ is the critical condition for obtaining a stable 3D octahedral network and any deviation from this scale will led to an undesired octahedral distortion of perovskites. The possibility of octahedral coordination of B site cation and X site anions can be predicted by octahedral factor (normally between 0.4 and 0.9).[38] The structural rigidity of 3D perovskites impedes its compositional tunability and the reduced dimensionality has emerged as a promising alternative. The lower dimensional perovskites (quasi-3D, quasi-layered, layered, 1D and 0D), are conceptually derived from cutting the 3D perovskites along its crystallographic planes, gradually to get rid of the tolerance factor curtailment.

The choice of crystallographic plane of slicing leads to formation of three different layered perovskite families with orientation along $\langle 100 \rangle$, $\langle 110 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$. The thickness of inorganic quantum well (QW, $p = n, m, q$ for $\langle 100 \rangle$, $\langle 110 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ oriented perovskites respectively) plays a crucial role in determining the optoelectronic and structural properties of layered perovskites and there by its PV compatibility. The inorganic QW thickness determines the dimensionality of layered perovskite; $p=1$ represents pristine layered perovskites whereas $1 < p \leq 7$ termed as quasi-layered. The layered perovskites with higher p values reported to have a mix phases of layered, quasi-layered and 3D and known as quasi-3D; moreover, the boundary condition of $p = \infty$ indicate the 3D perovskite structure.[1]

The occurrence of $\langle 110 \rangle$ oriented layered perovskites are less common due to the availability of few suitable spacer cations. They are known as corrugated layered

structures due to the high degree of octahedral distortions. Mostly, perovskites with corrugation length (number of octahedra in each corrugation unit) of 2×2 are reported and the extension of corrugation length to 3×3 and 4×4 could be possible by rational choice of spacer cations with site specific hydrogen bonding and other secondary bonding interactions.[39] As of now, corrugated layered perovskites are being synthesized mainly for $m = 1$ (thickness of QW) and its octahedral distortions forms self-trapped states to deliver white light emission at room temperature.[40] Slicing of 3D perovskites along $\langle 111 \rangle$ plane creates metal deficient structure hence the $\langle 111 \rangle$ oriented layered perovskites are rarely reported. The slicing along the body diagonal will eliminate the metal site whereas neutral BX_2 fragments are wiped in other two cases and the charge neutrality is only maintained for B^{+3} (Bi, Sb or As) or mixture of B^{+2} and B^{+3} metal cations. The p -type nature of $\langle 111 \rangle$ layered perovskites can be explored for future PV applications; provided its strong excitonic character may limit the device performances.[1, 41] Unlike the $\langle 110 \rangle$ and $\langle 111 \rangle$ oriented perovskites, $\langle 100 \rangle$ family is the most explored layered perovskites for solar cell applications. $\langle 100 \rangle$ oriented layered perovskites have been further classified into three groups depending on their structure such as Ruddlesden-Popper (RP), Dion-Jacobson (DJ) and alternating cation in the interlayer space (ACI).

Fig. 2 Structural comparison among RP (a,b,c) , DJ (d,e,f) and ACI (g,h,i) perovskites with inorganic layer thickness of $n = 3$. Reproduced with permission from ref. [29], from The American Chemical Society, Copyright 2018.

The widely used RP perovskites has a structure of $A'_2A_{n-1}B_nX_{3n+1}$, where A' is bulky alkyl or arylammonium cation spacer (Propylammonium- PA^+ , Butylammonium- BA^+ , Phenylethylammonium- PEA^+). Conceptual slicing along the $\langle 100 \rangle$ plane and subsequent introduction of larger mono ammonium spacer cations generate the RP perovskites where inorganic sheets shows a $[1/2, 1/2]$ displacement along the ab -plane. Thus, formed staggered structure with a bilayer of spacer cations between inorganic QWs creates a van der Waals gap.[42] On the other hand, the DJ perovskites replaces the monovalent spacer

cation by a divalent cation in order to reduce the interlayer distance. The DJ perovskites are formed with $A'A_{n-1}B_nX_{3n+1}$ general formula and shows no shift along the ab-plane. The removal of van der Waals gap by the divalent cations in DJ perovskites is proposed to improve the charge carrier dynamics which will be discussed in the following sections.[43] Additionally, the introduction of two cations simultaneously in to the inter layer space forms a new type of quasi-layered perovskite structure with a (1/2, 0) shift along ab-plane. The resultant formed ACI structure is believed as an intermediate between RP and DJ, since its structural features is similar to DJ and chemical formula to RP perovskites.[44] (Fig. 2) depicts the structure of RP, DJ and ACI perovskites and it is worth noting that the n value is determined according to the stoichiometric ratio of precursors added in the solution and not from the synthesized quasi-layered perovskites. The mixed dimensional layered/3D (Quasi 3D) perovskite absorbers are prepared by small addition of layered perovskites into 3D perovskites to partially replace the small amounts of organic cations with the bulky organic ones. Additionally, thin layer of layered perovskites is overlaid on the top of 3D perovskites absorber to form an interfacial layer. More precisely, the layered perovskites are categorized into pure layered, quasi-layered and quasi-3D where the n values vary between 1, $1 < n \leq 7$ and higher n values respectively.

3. Basic Optoelectronic Properties

3.1 Band structure and optical properties.

In 3D halide perovskites, the organic cation has no significant role in determining the electronic structure, where the conduction band maximum (CBM) is donated by Pb, p orbitals and the valence band maximum (VBM) derives from a combination of Pb, s and I p orbitals. The organic cations {methyl ammonium, (MA)/formamidinium FA} are majorly employed to full fill the stability and charge neutrality requirements. While the layered/quasi-layered perovskites composed of large-sized organic cation interlayer between the inorganic sheets act as a barrier for charge carriers.[45] The optical band gap (E_g) of layered/quasi-layered perovskites are much higher than that of corresponding 3D counterparts. The structural distortions, primarily the I-Pb-I bond angle in equatorial plane and the length of the organic spacer strongly alter optical band gap.[46] The high band gap, originated from the quantum confinement, can be narrowed by manipulating the thickness of QW (n value); for example, the E_g values decreases from 2.24 eV ($n = 1$) to 1.52 eV ($n = \infty$) for $BA_2MA_{n-1}Pb_nI_{3n+1}$ (Fig. 3c).[42] Moreover, the size and

electronegativity of metal and halide ions has significant impact on determining the E_g of perovskite; where, heavier halides and lighter metal ions favors the lower bandgap. The substitution of Pb with smaller Sn can help to lower the layered perovskite band gap which will also avoid the toxicity burden. This, flexibility of the band gap tuning for the layered/3D perovskite yield materials with desired optoelectronic properties. To note here, absorption spectrum contains the exciton absorption peak and the commonly used Tauc plot equation is no longer valid for RP perovskites. Thus, the Tauc plot cannot be used to calculate the optical band gap of RP perovskites. Since the absorption of layered materials are step-like near the band gap, E_g can be determined from that step-like onset at low temperature.

There is a significant dielectric constant contrast between the organic spacer and the inorganic part in layered perovskites. The small dielectric constants of larger organic cation (2.2 and 3.3 of BA and PEA respectively) creates the dielectric confinement in layered perovskites.[47] The combined effect of quantum confinement and the dielectric confinement develops high exciton binding energy in order of ~100-500 meV while the 3D analogue has ~30 meV (Fig. **3a,b**). The enhanced coulombic interactions between the bound carriers (electron-hole pairs) is detrimental for PV application since the electron-hole pair separation becomes difficult. Debates are going on the exact nature of optical transitions; RP perovskites with $n = 1$ is believed to form excitons while the 3D counterpart to form free-charge carriers at room temperature.[48] The uncertainty of optical transition mechanism in RP perovskites with intermediate n values was originated from the lack of fundamental knowledge of the dielectric constants, excited reduced mass etc. Blancon et al. demonstrated a scaling law [49] for calculating the exciton binding energy in layered perovskites as,

$$E_{b,1s} = \frac{E_0}{\left\{1 + \frac{\alpha - 3}{2}\right\}^2}, \text{ with } \alpha = 3 - \gamma e^{-\frac{L_w}{2a_0}}$$

Where E_0 (16meV) and a_0 (4.6 nm) are the 3D Rydberg energy and Bohn radius of 3D analogue, respectively. They introduced an empirical correction factor γ (1.76) to include the effect of dielectric confinement along with the quantum confinement on the exciton ground state binding energy. L_w is the physical width of quantum well for an infinite quantum well potential barrier. They have demonstrated that the free-carrier formation starts from RP perovskites with $n > 20$. Thus, in the RP perovskites with lower n values ($1 < n < 20$), the enhanced exciton binding energy (~100-500 meV) is much higher than the

thermal energy at room temperature ($K_B T = 2507$ meV); the photogenerated excitons are stable at room temperature and difficult to create free-carriers. Strategies have been adopted to decrease the exciton binding energy in literature, which includes the introduction of aromatic spacer cations with higher dielectric constant (PEA-3.3) over the aliphatic spacers (BA-2.2), stoichiometric mixing of aromatic cations, use of mixed halides and post-synthetic I_2 molecular intercalation.[50-53] Recently evolved Quasi-layered DJ perovskites demonstrated with reduced exciton binding energy due to smaller degree of distortion in their crystal structure. DJ perovskites with $n \geq 3$ are reported with lower E_b of 30-70 meV, which is comparable with the 3D analogues.

3.2 Charge carrier transport

The performance of PSCs is strictly depended on the efficient transport of photogenerated excitons and their subsequent annihilation to free-carriers. The instantaneous generation of free-carriers takes place in 3D perovskites owing to their small exciton binding energy. On the other hand, the carrier transport in layered perovskites is a complex phenomenon that relies on in-plane and out-of-plane distortions, Pb-I distance, I-Pb-I bond angle, exciton binding energy, and trap sites etc.[54] 3D perovskites are known to show the transition from electronic conduction to ionic conduction at high temperature (>280 K) under dark and illumination conditions which is detrimental for the perovskite stability and thus device performances.[55] Huang and co-workers reported a constant electronic conduction from quasi-layered perovskites along the in-plane and out-of-plane directions. Temperature dependent conductivity measurements unravel that above 280K the activation energy increases from 22 meV to 830 meV for $MAPbI_3$, overcoming the activation energy for ionic conduction i.e., 190 meV, while the quasi-layered $BA_2MA_2Pb_3I_{10}$ showed a constant value of 25 and 41 meV along the in-plane and out-of-plane directions respectively. Authors attributed this unique property of quasi-layered perovskites to its reduced vacancy defects over the 3D analogue where, the calculated defect formation energies showed a significant increase of $\sim 1.2-2$ eV for both the MA and I vacancies.[56-57] Although the electronic conduction is dominated for quasi-layered perovskites, the charge carrier transportation is restricted to have a layered-planar like behavior, which is distinct from 3D analogue. A dominant carrier conductivity and mobility along the out-of-plane orientation of crystallographic planes are highly favored in order to overcome the trade-off between the stability and efficiency of PSCs. The hot-casting method by Mohite et.al. demonstrating the out-of-plane orientation for the first time, considers as a milestone in layered perovskite based PSCs, where they improved

the PCE from 5% to in excess of 12%. [58] Additionally, the use additives, rational choice of spacer cation and different salt-assisted anti-solvent treatments yielded the vertical aligned perovskite thin films with enhanced crystallinity, large grain size and reduced defect sites. Moreover, functionalization of organic spacer cation is a widely explored route to improve the carrier transport. [59-62] Fluorination on the para position of PEA cation demonstrated to enhance the interlayer electronic coupling along with improved charge transport, longer charge carrier lifetime and reduced trap density. (F-PEA)₂PbI₄ showed seven times higher out-of-plane mobility than of (PEA)₂PbI₄, measured using a time-resolved microwave conductivity (TRMC). Authors employed conductive atomic force microscopy (C-AFM), TRMC, and time-resolved photoluminescence (TRPL) to understand the effect of fluorination in quasi-2D perovskites. TRMC showed an improved peak value of $\sim 9 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ for (F-PEA)₂MA₄Pb₅I₁₆ while the non-fluorinated analogue showed $\sim 7 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and the TRPL measurements showed a significant increase from 20 ns to 30 ns upon the fluorination. [60] The achieved higher mobility and longer carrier lifetime without the use of any additives or the hot-casting method highlights the spacer cation functionalization as a promising tool.

Fig. 3 (a) Confinement effects in layered perovskites, Reproduced with permission from ref.[63] (b) experimental binding energy of the exciton ground state (1s) and the excited exciton states (2s, 3s, 4s), and comparison to theoretical results for the exciton ground state, Reproduced with permission from ref. [49] (c) Comparative band energy diagram of the RP perovskite compounds ($\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_{n-1}\text{Pb}_n\text{I}_{3n+1}$). Reproduced with permission from ref. [83] (d) illustrate the carrier transport pathway through a multiphase layered perovskite. Reproduced with permission from ref. [104] (e) Schematic diagram of operation mechanism of quasi-layered perovskite photovoltaics and the correlation between band structure, energy disorder, and V_{oc} of the device. Reproduced with permission from ref. [65]

Along with the vertically oriented crystal growth, the thickness of inorganic cage (n value) contributes to the charge-transfer behavior. To date, most of the reports suggests that the crystallization of quasi-layered perovskites is followed by the formation of multiple $\langle n \rangle$ value species with a random distribution which delivers a desperate band gap. It is reported that the transit time of photogenerated carriers across the electrodes is longer than the cascade energy transfer time indicating that the carriers were relaxed near to band edge of the smallest band gap phase before the annihilation (Fig. 3d,e).[64] This cascade energy transfer between different phases results in the higher energy loss owing to the additional cooling process in the charge transportation and the band tail states created by the high degree of energy disorder that is known to induce significant V_{oc} loss in the PSCs. To overcome such barrier, noticeable steps has been taken and a narrow phase distribution has been proposed to mitigate such issues.[65] Rational choice of spacer cations, additive engineering and manipulated fabrication processes has been employed in order to achieve the homogeneous phase distribution (discussed in the next part). However, these approaches still lack the understanding of crystallization kinetics that needs to be explored further to overcome the tradeoff between device stability and efficiency.

The charge carrier dynamics in layered/3D mixed dimensional PSCs and their role in influencing the device performance has not been reported in details. Investigations has been demonstrated that small addition of large organic cations increases the crystallinity and reduces the trap mediated charge recombination thereby increasing the effective charge carrier mobility of the hybrid perovskite. The layered capping layer atop of the 3D hybrid perovskite can also enhance the subtle excitonic effects and effectively passivate the trap states thereby lowering the non-radiative charge recombination.

Fig. 4 (a) Crystal structure of MAPbI_3 and $(\text{PEA})_2(\text{MA})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (b) PXRD pattern of films $(\text{PEA})_2(\text{MA})_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$, left; MAPbI_3 formed from PbI_2 , middle; MAPbI_3 formed from PbCl_2 , right-exposed to 52% humidity. Reproduced with permission figure (a-b) from ref. [69] (c) Photos of films incorporating bare FAPbI_3 , FAPbI_3 with layered perovskite and $\text{FA}_{0.98}\text{Cs}_{0.02}\text{PbI}_3$ with layered perovskite to relative humidity of 80% for different time (d) Evolution of absorption of films at 600 nm at RH 80% at 20°C. Reproduced with permission figure (c-d) from ref.[66] (e) XRD pattern of $(\text{PDA})(\text{MA})_3\text{Pb}_4\text{I}_{13}$ at different hot casting temperature (f) UV/vis spectra of 2D perovskite with different values. Reproduced with permission figure (e-f) from ref.[43]

4. Stability of layered multidimensional PSCs

Currently, the main issue with PSCs is the device stability that restricts their outdoor PV application.[67] To date, the progress in PV performances of PSCs such as improved efficiencies via different device architect, fabrication methods and studying of underlying mechanisms have been taken into account. However, the stability of PSCs remains always a key challenge. A series of chemical reactions undergoes in the perovskite films under different atmospheric conditions such as moisture, oxygen, UV light and temperature.[68] These conditions allow the perovskite to combine with other components that leads to the decomposition of the perovskite films and affecting the stability of the PSC. Sincere efforts have been devoted to improving the stability of PSCs and impressive progress is achieved with compositional engineering of the perovskite layer, interface modification, tolerance factor adjustment, surface passivation, encapsulation and additive processing. Thus, the issues of the degradation of the perovskite and stability of the PSCs is being addressed in order to achieve reproducibility and longer lifetime. Another postulate to suppressing the undesirable degradation of PSCs, is the usage of the layered (2D) or quasi layered perovskite composed of bulky organic cations. Unlike the small organic cations in the 3D perovskites, these layered bulky organic cations provide steric hindrance for the surface water adsorption and can block the accessible pathway for moisture invasion.

Arguably, the stability of the PSCs has been reported in the literature where RP layered PSCs showed better stability compared to their 3D analogues, due to the presence of ammonium cations between the layers that provide weak van der waals (vdW) interactions and the DJ layered perovskites has the diammonium cations that offers alternate hydrogen bonding between the organic and inorganic layers for structural stability of PSCs. However, both RP and DJ perovskites shows lower PV performances because of their wide optical band gaps that forbids sufficient light absorption and better charge transport. Layered/3D perovskite layers contributes to both the long-term stability and device performance. The bulky alkyl chain cations in the layered perovskites contributes to moisture shielding while the 3D perovskite counterpart facilitates the charge transport properties.

One of the primary factors responsible for the instability in the perovskites is the moisture or a humid environment. Moisture could easily penetrate into the perovskite films with low hydrophobicity that consequently leads to degradation of the layer making it photo-inactive. Incorporation of layered perovskite with large aromatic or aliphatic ammonium cations make the perovskite films more hydrophobic, tolerant to moisture and effectively

prevents the permeation of water (Fig. 4c, d). Karunadasa et al reported the quasi-2D perovskite ($\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$; $n=3$) and the quasi 2D perovskite film showed improved stability when stored in ambient conditions with relative humidity (RH) of 52 % after 40 days (Fig. 4a,b)[69], while the MAPbI_3 films degraded in 4-5 days. Kanatzidis and co-workers showed the smooth and high surface coverage in quasi-2D $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_{n-1}\text{Pb}_n\text{I}_{3n+1}$ film that is moisture resistant and stable after 2 months of exposure under 40% humidity environment.[70] A high quality $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_3\text{Pb}_4\text{I}_{13}$ ($n=4$) film deposited by hot casting deposition was demonstrated to show a much more compact and uniform thin film with larger grain size and fewer pinholes. By optimizing the amount of both bulky and small organic cation, the dimensionality of the layered perovskite can be tuned. For instance, Sargent et al incorporated PEAI into MAPbI_3 solution to form $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_{n-1}\text{Pb}_n\text{I}_{3n+1}$ that showed good performance longevity after storage at RH 55% under dark for 14 days.[71] Also, PEAI was introduced with FAPbI_3 perovskite to form mixed-cation $\text{FA}_x\text{PEA}_{1-x}\text{PbI}_3$ that improved both the phase and stability of the perovskite films.[72]

Temperature plays another elemental role in degradation pathway of perovskite. The thermal decomposition of the perovskite film occurs under continuous thermal stress that leads to triggering of ion migration and thus the escaped ion diffuses into the top electrode hindering the hole transporting layer (HTL) and metal contact. The thermal stress at high temperature deteriorates the light absorbing capability and thereby affects the charge transport mechanism and overall device performance. Besides, the chemical decomposition and phase transition also are induced due to thermal increment. An alternative strategy to prevent the thermal decomposition of perovskite film is to substitute the small organic cation with the large bulky groups of layered perovskites to enhance the thermal stability (Fig. 4e, f). Lin and co-workers introduced a method to form a layered/3D $(\text{BA})_2\text{PbI}_4$ structure by spin coating *n*-butylamine (BA) atop of MAPbI_3 perovskite film that provided better stability and prevents the film from degradation.[73]

Scheme 1: Chemical structures based on the large ammonium cations reported for the layered hybrid perovskites

5. Application in photovoltaics

We screen recent reports on the application of quasi layered ($1 < n \leq 5$) and layered/3D perovskites in PSCs. For the ease of reading, we have organized this section in to three parts. The PSCs with i) quasi-layered perovskites, ii) layered/3D perovskites and iii) emerging lead free low dimensional perovskites. We discuss in detail how the compositional engineering, additive engineering, new process for perovskite deposition and fabrication techniques influence device long-term stability, charge carrier dynamics, and the performance. Scheme 1 shows the chemical structure of the large organic cations commonly used in layered hybrid perovskites.

5.1. Quasi-layered PSCs.

For quasi-layered perovskites, the structural diversification of organic spacer cations has been the major research focus in recent years. In this section we have reviewed the RP and DJ perovskites-based PSCs separately and each section are divided further into devices with aliphatic and aromatic spacer cations.

5.1.1. Ruddlesden-Popper Perovskites

The relevant works on RP Perovskite based PSCs are listed in Table 1 and the salient features are summarized as follows.

Aromatic spacer cation: Smith et al. reported first Ruddlesden-Popper perovskite with $n = 3$ by introducing an aromatic spacer cation (PEA) in conventional MAPbI₃. [69] The RP perovskites layers fabricated by a single step spin coating technique at room temperature, showed exceptional stability up to 40 days storage at ambient atmosphere, where the 3D counterpart degraded within 4-5 days. Although, the first-generation PSCs fabricated in an $n-i-p$ fashion, yielded comparatively low PCE of 4.73%, it emerged as a promising candidate due to high open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) of 1.18 V. The poor device performance was attributed to low short-circuit current (J_{sc}). Later, Ma and his coworkers demonstrated an inverted planar device with PEA₂MA _{$n-1$} Pb _{n} I _{$3n+1$} ($n = 3,4,5$), where they compared the effects of room temperature spin coating and hot-casting methods of film fabrication and inorganic QW thickness on device performance. [74] The PSCs fabricated with $n = 4$ RP perovskites layers by hot-casting method showed best PCE of 5.5% with an improved J_{sc} of 9.64 mA/cm². The RP, PSC retained 50% and 65% of PCE after thermal stress (100 °C) for 70 hours and moisture stress (72% RH) for 90 hours respectively. Also, the unencapsulated RP, PSCs showed a constant PCE for 65 hours in a photostability test while the 3D counterpart retained only 60% of initial PCE. However, these improvements in the stability have been followed by a decline in the device performance due to the poor charge transport between the inorganic sheets and a vertical aligned perovskite crystal growth is known to mitigate the issue. It is well reported that the introduction of additives to the precursor solution is effective to tune the crystallization in 3D perovskites. Due to the similar radius of pseudohalide thiocyanate ion (SCN⁻) with I⁻ and the possible strong interactions between Pb²⁺ and lone pairs of electrons of S and N from SCN⁻, thiocyanate salts were used as additives in 3D-PSCs. Fu *et al.* used ammonium thiocyanate (NH₄SCN) and ammonium chloride (NH₄Cl) additives simultaneously, to improve the crystallinity of PEA₂MA₄Pb₅I₁₆ ($n = 5$) and impel a preferential orientation of crystallographic planes

perpendicular to the electrodes. NH_4Cl boosted the V_{oc} from 1.11 to 1.21 V and the Cl^- passivation on electron traps near the HTL-perovskite interface reduced the non-radiative recombination. The $J-V$ and external quantum efficiency (EQE) curves (Fig. 5a,b) validate the collective roles of both additives in displaying a significant rise in the PCE to 14.1% with lowest V_{oc} loss of ~ 0.16 V.[75]

The low device performance can be further attributed to a synergistic effect of quantum and dielectric confinement in the RP perovskites and Pan et al. proposed an alternative by functionalization of PEA with electron withdrawing halogen atoms.[76] fluoro- (F), chloro-(Cl), and bromo-(Br) groups were substituted on the *para-position* in the prototypical H-PEA cation which in turn reduced the binding energy and the bandgap. Out of all the compositions, F- $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ exhibiting lowest binding energy and comparable low band gap showed better PCE of 5.8%. Later Zhang et al. boosted the device efficiency to 13.64% with a F- $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_4\text{Pb}_5\text{I}_{16}$ ($n = 5$) RP layer fabricated by an anti-solvent treatment, additionally, F-PEA based device displayed enhanced thermal stability than H-PEA counterpart, without any additives.[77] Fu et al. and Shi et al. further improved the PCE of F- $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_4\text{Pb}_5\text{I}_{16}$ to 14.5% and 17.3% respectively, by employing NH_4SCN additive.[62, 78] Yang et al. extended the choice of aromatic spacer cation beyond the PEA to benzylammonium (BEN) and 3-bromobenzylammonium (3BBEN). The inverted planar PSCs fabricated from BEN and 3BBEN yielded a competitive PCE of 13.33% and 18.20% respectively with the incorporation of MACl additive. Along with the exceptional moisture stability of unencapsulated device that retain 82% of original efficiency after 2400 hours at relative humidity of 40%, 3BBEN based device showed constant PV parameters after 60s immersion in water.[79]

Fig. 5 (a) J - V and (b) EQE Graphs of NH_4SCN and NH_4Cl treated RP perovskite-based PSCs. Reproduced with permission from ref. [75] (c-f) GIWAXS maps for polycrystalline RP perovskite films with MACI/MAI weight ratios of (c) 0, (d) 0.3, (e) 0.5 and (f) 1.0, (g) TRPL spectra of the thin films with MACI/MAI weight ratios of 0 and 0.5. (h) J - V and (i) MPP tracking parameters of ITO/PEDOTPSS/ $\text{ThMA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ /PCBM/BCP/Ag. Reproduced with permission figure (c-i) from ref. [80], The American Chemical Society, Copyright 2018.

The aromatic spacer cation pool is further widened by the introduction of 2-thiophenemethylammonium (TMA) iodide by Chen and his co-workers with an efficiency $>15\%$. The $\text{TMA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ with MACl additive induced the growth of dense web of nanorod-like film in which the out-of-plane orientation is highly favored and improved carrier lifetime (Fig. 5c-i).[80] Narrow phase distribution and vertical crystal orientation of RP perovskites layers are the key features for efficient PSCs fabrication. The film fabrication either by the introduction of additives or at high temperature has been used to improve the crystal orientation. Irrespective of the fabrication techniques,

the control over phase distribution of vertically aligned RP perovskites layers was limited when the precursor solutions were made by stoichiometric mixing of precursor components in polar solvents. The broad phase distribution of lower and higher $\langle n \rangle$ values of RP perovskites will induce more non-radiative recombination and charge trap sites which will eventually reduce the device performance. Qin et al. adapted a new approach where; RP perovskite layers were fabricated from a colloidal solution of pre-synthesized RP perovskite single crystals which narrowed the phase distribution. [81] The colloidal RP perovskites nano-crystals acted as a template and demonstrated a bottom-to-top crystal growth. Permutation and combination of polar/non-polar solvents played a crucial role in the phase distribution control and was systematically studied through various techniques such as photoluminescence, transient absorption and trap density calculations. The RP perovskites single crystals of $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$, $\text{TMA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ and $\text{TEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ (TEA- 2-Thiophene ethylammonium) was prepared and their corresponding colloidal solution in DMAc:Tol:HI (DMAc- Dimethylacetamide, Tol-Toluene, HI- Hydroiodic acid) solvent used as the precursor solution. The RP perovskites layers fabricated by hot-casting of heated precursor solution followed by a post annealing treatment delivered an absorber layer with exceptional vertical orientation with a narrow phase distribution from $n = 2$ (bottom) to $n = 4$ (top). While the combination of polar co-solvents (DMSO) with DMAc resulted in a broad distribution where lower n -phases ($n = 1,2$) and $n = \infty$ phases were arranged from bottom to top surface (Fig. 6d). The fabricated inverted planar PSCs in ITO/Cu:NiOx/RP-perovskites/PCBM/BCP/Ag fashion displayed a competitive PCE of 14.68% with V_{oc} of 1.23 V, J_{sc} of 15.85mA/cm² and FF of 75.3% for $\text{TEA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ without the use of any additives, a superior stability of 93% of initial efficiency retainment was achieved after 500 hours of unencapsulated operation under ambient air conditions (Fig. 6a-c). The exceptional increase in V_{oc} was attributed to the vertically aligned narrow phase distribution of RP perovskites. Recently, Liu and his co-workers introduced a new aromatic FA derivative, 2-Thiophenformamidinium (TFA), as the spacer cation.[82] Thus fabricated $\text{TFA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ based inverted planar PSC reported a PCE of 16.72% with a precursor organic-salt assisted crystal growth method, where a dilute solution of precursor organic salts in isopropanol was applied as the anti-solvent.

Table 1. Photovoltaic performance and stability of relevant RP Perovskite based PSCs

Perovskite	n	Device configuration	PCE (%)	Stability
Aromatic spacer				
PEA ₂ MA ₂ Pb ₃ I ₁₀	3	FTO/c-TiO ₂ /PSK/Spiro-OMeTAD/Au	4.73	N/A
PEA ₂ MA ₃ Pb ₄ I ₁₃	4	ITO/PEDOT:PSS/PSK/PCBM/Ag	5.5	Unencapsulated device retained 50% of initial stability after 90h storage at 72% RH
PEA ₂ MA ₄ Pb ₅ I ₁₆	5	ITO/PEDOT:PSS/PSK/PCBM/BCP/Ag	14.1	Retention of >90% PCE after 45 days in dark at 30% RH
F-PEA ₂ MA ₂ Pb ₃ I ₁₀	3	FTO/NiO _x /PSK/PC61BM/BCP/Ag	5.83	N/A
F-PEA ₂ MA ₄ Pb ₅ I ₁₆	5	FTO/c-TiO ₂ /PSK/Spiro-OMeTAD/Au	13.64	65% PCE retainment after 576h at 70 °C
F-PEA ₂ MA ₄ Pb ₅ I ₁₆	5	ITO/PEDOT:PSS/PSK/PCBM/BCP/Ag	14.5	90% of PCE after 40 days, 40-50% RH storage
4-FPEA ₂ MA ₄ Pb ₅ I ₁₆	5	ITO/PTAA/PSK/PCBM/PEI/Ag	17.3	93% of PCE after 500h storage at 55% RH; constant PCE after 500h of thermal aging at 55 °C
3BBA _{1.8} MA _{2.5} Pb ₃ I _{(1-x)Cl_x} ⁽⁶¹⁾	3	ITO/PTAA/PSK/PCBM/Cr/Ag	18.2	82% PCE after 2400h storage at 40% RH, 100% PCE after 60s immersion in water
ThMA ₂ MA ₂ Pb ₃ I ₁₀	3	ITO/PEDOT:PSS/PSK/PCBM/BCP/Ag	15.42	90% PCE after 1000h storage under N ₂
TEA ₂ MA ₂ Pb ₃ I ₁₀	3	ITO/Cu:NiO _x /PSK/PCBM/BCP/Ag	14.68	93% PCE after 500h storage under ambient condition
ThFA ₂ MA ₂ Pb ₃ I ₁₀	3	ITO/PEDOT:PSS/PSK/PCBM/BCP/Ag	16.72	99% of PCE after 3000h storage under N ₂ , 90% of PCE after light soaking for 216h.
ThMA ₂ FA ₄ Pb ₅ I ₁₆	5	ITO/PEDOT:PSS/PSK/PCBM/BCP/Ag	19.06	99% of PCE after 552h at 30% RH, 96% of PCE after 576h at 80 °C under N ₂ .
Aliphatic spacer				
BA ₂ MA ₂ Pb ₃ I ₁₀	3	FTO/c-TiO ₂ /mp-TiO ₂ /PSK/Spiro-OMeTAD/Au	4.02	N/A
BA ₂ MA ₃ Pb ₄ I ₁₃	4	ITO/PEDOT:PSS/PSK/PCBM/Al	12.52	20% of PCE after 60h storage at 65% RH
iso-BA ₂ MA ₃ Pb ₄ I ₁₃	4	FTO/C ₆₀ /PSK/Spiro-OMeTAD/Au	10.63	N/A
Cs ⁺ :BA ₂ MA ₃ Pb ₄ I ₁₃	4	FTO/TiO ₂ /PSK/Spiro-OMeTAD/Au	13.68	89% of PCE after 1400h storage at 30% RH, 85% of PCE after 12h at 80 °C
BA ₂ (MA _{0.8} FA _{0.2}) ₃ Pb ₄ I ₁₃	4	ITO/PEDOT:PSS/PSK/PCBM/BCP/Ag	12.81	88% of PCE after 1300h storage at 46-60% RH
BA ₂ MA ₃ Pb ₄ I ₁₃	4	ITO/PEDOT:PSS/PSK/PCBM/PEIE/Ag	14.9	N/A

BA ₂ MA ₃ Pb ₄ I ₁₃	4	ITO/PTAA/PSK/C60/BCP/Ag	17.26	>95% of PCE after 2000h storage under N ₂
Li ⁺ :BA ₂ MA ₃ Pb ₄ I ₁₃	4	ITO/PEDOT:PSS/PSK/PCBM/Ag	14.9	80% of PCE after 240h storage at 30% RH
PA ₂ MA ₄ Pb ₅ I ₁₆	5	FTO/c-TiO ₂ /PSK/Spiro-OMeTAD/Au	10.41	>90% of PCE after 500h storage at 50-60% RH
(PEA _{1-x} BA _x) ₂ MA ₃ Pb ₄ I ₁₃	4	ITO/PTAA/PSK/PCBM/BCP/Ag	15.7	88% of PCE after 30 days storage at 40-50% RH
(PBA _{0.5} BA _{0.5}) ₂ MA ₃ Pb ₄ I ₁₃	4	ITO/PTAA/PSK/PCBM/BCP/Ag	16	60.85 and 93% of PCE after 30days under heat (80 °C), light and moisture (40% RH) aging respectively
MTEA ₂ MA ₄ Pb ₅ I ₁₆	5	ITO/PEDOT:PSS/PSK/PCBM/Cr/Ag	18.06	87.1% of PCE after 1000h of MPP tracking under N ₂

In another report, the use of FA as the small cation in RP perovskites. TMA₂FA₄Pb₅I₁₆ ($n = 5$) based PSCs gave an improved PCE of 16.18% where the MA counterpart (TMA₂MA_(n-1)Pb_nI_(3n+1)) earlier gave a relatively low PCE of ~15%. The improvement in PCE was mainly attributed to the increase in the J_{sc} from 18.89 to 22.53 mA/cm². The PCE was boosted further to 19.06%, to a record value of any aromatic spacer cation based RP PSCs with $n \leq 5$, with an organic-salt assisted crystal growth (OACG) as depicted in (Fig. 6e).[83] Although, the random distribution of n -phase was noted by GIWAXS and HRTEM analysis, OACG treated RP perovskites exhibited reduced trap density, decreased non-radiative recombination losses and enhanced charge carrier mobility that led to the record PCE. The environmental stability of both RP perovskites layers and the device were studied systematically and an excellent long-term stability with 99% and 96% of original PCE retainment after 552-hour storage in ambient condition (RH, 30 ± 5%) and 576 hours of thermal stress (at 80 °C) under N₂ condition respectively was reported.

Aliphatic spacer Cation: Taking the inspiration from first quasi-layered RP based, Cao *et al.* fabricated BA (Butylammonium) based quasi-layered perovskite absorbers with varying QW thickness ($n = 1 - 4$) through spin coating at room temperature.[84] The champion device with $n = 3$, RP perovskite based absorber showed a similar PCE of 4.02% with improved short-circuit current of 9.42 mA/cm². The absorber layer was formed in a self-assembly fashion where the crystal growth was preferentially oriented perpendicular to the substrate layer, favoring the surface coverage and the charge

transport. However, the possibility of rapid crystallization and anisotropic charge transport were still alive with the room temperature single step spin coating technique and thus the PCE lagged behind that of 3D counterpart. In 2016, Tsai *et al.* in a seminal report an alternative hot casting technique adopted which later became a standard approach for fabrication of layered perovskites, where the perovskite precursor solution was spun coated on a preheated substrate, resulting in a uniform surface, reflective and more vertically oriented films.[58] Thus demonstrated planar PSCs with strong preferential out-of-plane orientation of $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_3\text{Pb}_4\text{I}_{13}$ ($n = 4$) showed a remarkable jump in PCE to 12.52% with negligible hysteresis. The hot casting method not only improved the charge transport by lowering the defect density and increasing the depletion region to allow more effective collection of photo generated carriers but also retarded the recombination, which lifted the FF and J_{sc} to 74.13% and 16.76 mA/cm^2 respectively. Zhang et al. introduced NH_4SCN additive to $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ ($n = 4$) to improve the vertical orientation of RP perovskites and reduce the non-radiative recombination. The ITO/PEDOT:PSS/RP-perovskites/PCBM/BCP/Ag device displayed a PCE of 8.79% without using hot-casting method.[85] In a separate study, BA was replaced with iso-butylamine (iso-BA) and fabricated at room temperature, the device performance was improved for to 8.82%.[86] However, the devices with iso- $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_3\text{Pb}_4\text{I}_{13}$ ($n = 4$) absorber suffered from high $J-V$ hysteresis value. Inorganic cationic doping is an effective tool to improve the stability and efficiency; Cs^+ and Rb^+ has been widely explored in order to enhance the crystallinity and crystallite size of MAPbI_3 . 5% Cs^+ doping in $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_3\text{Pb}_4\text{I}_{13}$ ($n = 4$) enhanced the performance of FTO/ TiO_2 / Cs_x -layered perovskites/Spiro-MeOTAD/Au solar cell to 13.7%. The Lewis acid-base adduct formation upon the addition of DMSO to neat DMF in the previously reported hot-cast method, also improved the crystallization. The synergistic effect of Cs^+ and DMSO improved the storage stability of unencapsulated device after 1400 hour at 30% RH condition, from 74% to 89% of initial PCE.[87] Moreover, higher moisture and thermal stability was demonstrated with Cs^+ doping. Later, Soe et al. also systematically studied the effect of DMSO:DMF mixed solvent in attaining a highly crystalline vertically oriented $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_4\text{Pb}_5\text{I}_{16}$ ($n = 5$) RP perovskites and reported a PCE of 10% with an improved photo-response.[88] FA based 3D perovskite systems have lower bandgap as compared to MAPbI_3 . Interestingly, FA based $\text{BA}_2\text{FA}_{n-1}\text{Pb}_n\text{I}_{3n+1}$ ($n = 1-5$) RP perovskites was developed by Chen and the ITO/PEDOT:PSS/ $\text{BA}_2\text{FA}_2\text{Pb}_3\text{I}_{10}$ /PC₆₁BM/BCP/Ag device showed a competitive PCE of 6.88% with a thiourea-assisted fabrication technique.[89] Later, 20% A site alloyed RP

perovskites ($\text{BA}_2(\text{MA}_{0.8}\text{FA}_{0.2})_3\text{Pb}_4\text{I}_{13}$) was developed by Zhou *at el.* displayed 12.81% PCE, where the reference ($\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_3\text{Pb}_4\text{I}_{13}$) yielded only 10.7%. [90]

Although the hot-casting technique is widely used, it is difficult to maintain the precise substrate temperature throughout the spin coating process, which limits the batch-to-batch reproducibility and paves the way for alternatives. Spin-coating free methods, i.e., drop-casting method and slot-die process, were introduced by Gao et al. During the drop-casting, the precursor solution was dropped on a hot substrate to spread isotropically and undergoes crystallization by the solvent evaporation. Patterned RP perovskites layers were also fabricated by controlling the solution spreading with non-wetting boundaries. [91] The RP perovskites fabricated from drop-casting method in air displayed a certified PCE of 14.33% and the champion device showed 14.9% PCE having ITO/PEDOT:PSS/ $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_3\text{Pb}_4\text{I}_{13}$ /PCBM/PEIE/Ag configuration along with comparable environmental stability. The first report on the slot-die coated RP perovskites-based PSCs recorded 12.5% and 8% PCE for slot-die coated and roll-to-roll slot die coated flexible devices respectively.

In a separate study, slow-post annealing (with hot-casting) method was adopted to fabricate the $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_3\text{Pb}_4\text{I}_{13}$ ($n = 4$) film and measured an exceptional PCE of 17.26% and significant device storage stability, which was attributed to the fine gradient vertical alignment of multiple phases ($n = 1$ to $n = \infty$ from bottom to top surface). [92] Li et al. demonstrated the reduction in the dielectric confinement through the Li^+ doping in $\text{BA}_2\text{MA}_3\text{Pb}_4\text{I}_{13}$ ($n = 4$). Li^+ doping reduced the dielectric constant difference between the organic spacer cation (BA) and the inorganic framework to measure the PCE as ~15%. [93] Meanwhile, some more aliphatic spacer cations other than BA, were intercalated to RP perovskites-based PSCs. Liu and his co-workers employed *n*-propylammonium (PA) spacer cation ($n = 5$) and demonstrated a PSC with PCE of 10.41%. Although the PCE trailed behind the BA counterpart, $\text{PA}_2\text{MA}_4\text{Pb}_5\text{I}_{16}$ showed worthy stability; maintaining 98% of original PCE after 500-hour storage under 60% RH condition. [94]

Fig. 6 (a) J - V curve depicts the effects of solvents in device performance, (b) EQE and integrated J_{sc} curves of champion device with $TEA_2MA_2Pb_3I_{10}$ based PSC, (c) Stability parameters in different solvents (d) diagram showing the role of solvents in colloidal precursor solution in the formation of an ordered RP perovskite. Reproduced with permission figure (a-d) from ref. [81] (e) Schematics of different fabrication methods for layered perovskites, Reproduced with permission figure from ref. [83]

A recent report demonstrated a mixed spacer cation, where BA is partially replaced by MA to realize a highly oriented RP perovskite layer in out-of-plane direction ($BA_{2-x}MA_{3+x}Pb_4I_{13}$, $x = 0, 0.2, 0.4, \text{ and } 0.6$, $n = 4$).^{77} Li et al. compared the poor-reproducible hot-casting method and a non-preheated spin coating method (NP) to measure a comparable PCE of 16.29% and 15.44%. Additionally, the unencapsulated device displayed and improved stability than the reference device with $BA_2MA_3Pb_4I_{13}$ absorber. The binary spacer cation concept was adapted further by some groups, where they found that, introduction of binary spacer improves the preferential out-of-plane orientation, charge transport and eventually the device efficiency. PEA, GA (guanidinium), F3EA (trifluoroethylammonium) and PBA (4-phenylbutan-1-aminium) were blended with BA and the corresponding PSCs recorded decent PCEs near 16%. Additionally, the interplay of binary spacer on the surface morphology and trap sites were systematically investigated for $(PBA_{0.5}BA_{0.5})_2MA_3Pb_4I_{13}$.^[95-98]

Fig. 7 (a) Comparison of X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) spectra of the S(2p) and (b) X-ray absorption near edge structure (XANES) spectra of the S element of MTEACl films and (MTEA)₂(MA)₄Pb₅I₁₆ perovskite films. (c,d) harsh stability test parameters of (c)perovskite film and (d) devices Reproduced with permission figure from ref. [80]

Most recently, Ren et al. reported a joint experimental and theoretical study on the interlayer interactions of adjacent spacer cations, where they replaced BA completely with a new alkylammonium 2-(methylthio)ethylamine hydrochloride (MTEACl) spacer. The lone pairs of electrons in the S atom induce a strong molecular interaction between the close MTEA cations. The S-S interaction was further supported by the enhanced

interlayer binding energy and the charge density overlap obtained from first-principles density functional theory (DFT) calculations (Fig. 7a, b). MTEA showed improved out-of-plane orientation than the BA counter-part for $n = 5$ RP perovskite layer. The strengthened interlayer molecular interaction led to a record PCE of 18.06% by any aliphatic spacer-based RP base PSC to date. The fabricated ITO/PEDOT: PSS/RP perovskite/PCBM/Cr/Au device exhibited V_{oc} of 1.088 V, J_{sc} of 21.77 mA/cm² and a FF of 76.27%. Moreover, the environmental stability of MTEA₂MA₄Pb₅I₁₆ film and the long-term stability of unencapsulated device showed exceptional improvements in comparison with the BA₂MA₄Pb₅I₁₆ counterparts. Modified film was stable against the moisture (80% RH) and thermal stress (85 °C) for 1512 and 375 hours respectively, while the reference film showed comparatively faster degradation. The stability tests close to industrial harsh conditions emphasized the role of S-S interaction. Most importantly, the champion device retained its 87.1% of initial performance after continuous power output at the MPP (maximum power point) for 1,000 hour with a constant load of 0.90 V , where the reference device retained only 40% (Fig. 7c,d).[99]

5.1.2. Dion-Jacobson Perovskites

Recently emerged Dion-Jacobson (DJ) perovskites witnessed a considerable surge in the PCE as well as stability of PSCs in the last years. The DJ perovskites introduced by Kanatzidis [100] displayed improved conductivity/charge mobility and stability over the RP perovskites due to the presence diammonium cationic group, which could avoid the van der Waals gap formed in RP perovskites when the monoammonium groups interacted with inorganic part. We tabulated the influence of numerous DJ based perovskites in PSCs in Table 2.

Table 2. Summary of DJ Perovskite based PSCs

Perovskite	n	Device configuration	PCE (%)	Stability
<i>Aliphatic Spacer</i>				
3AMPMA ₃ Pb ₄ I ₁₃	4	FTO/PEDOT:PSS/PSK/C ₆₀ /BCP/Ag	7.32	N/A
4AMPMA ₃ Pb ₄ I ₁₃	4	FTO/PEDOT:PSS/PSK/C ₆₀ /BCP/Ag	4.24	N/A
3AMP(MA _{0.75} FA _{0.25}) ₃ Pb ₄ I ₁₃	4	FTO/PEDOT:PSS/PSK/C ₆₀ /BCP/Ag	12.04	22% of PCE after 48h under constant AM 1.5G illumination (50-70% RH)
PDAMA ₃ Pb ₄ I ₁₃	4	ITO/PEDOT:PSS/PSK/C ₆₀ /BCP/Ag	13	99% of PCE after 100h at 70 °C and 85% RH

PDAMA ₃ Pb ₄ I ₁₃	4	FTO/TiO ₂ /PSK/Spiro-OMeTAD/Au	13.3	>95% of PCE after i) 4000h at 40-70% RH, ii)168h at 85 °C and 85% RH and iii) 3000h of continuous light illumination
BDAMA _(n-1) Pb _n X _(3n+1)	5	ITO/PEDOT:PSS/PSK/PCBM/LiF/Au	17.91	84% of PCE after 1182h storage at ambient air; 90% of PCE after 298h of continuous illumination
DMAPAMA ₃ Pb ₄ I ₁₃	4	FTO/TiO ₂ /PSK/Spiro-OMeTAD/Au	15.16	90% of PCE after 1000h at 85 °C; 80% of PCE after 300h of continuous illumination
<i>Aromatic spacer</i>				
PDMAFA ₃ Pb ₄ I ₁₃	4	FTO/c-TiO ₂ /mp-TiO ₂ /PSK/Spiro-OMeTAD/Au	7.11	N/A
3AMPYMA ₃ Pb ₄ I ₁₃	4	FTO/PEDOT:PSS/PSK/C ₆₀ /BCP/Ag	9.2	N/A
4AMPYMA ₃ Pb ₄ I ₁₃	4	FTO/PEDOT:PSS/PSK/C ₆₀ /BCP/Ag	5.69	N/A
(ThDMA)MA ₄ Pb ₅ I ₁₆	5	ITO/PEDOT:PSS/PSK/PCBM/BCP/Ag	15.75	95% of PCE after 1655h storage under N ₂ ; 88% of PCE after 668h of continuous light soaking

Aliphatic Spacer cations: In the first report of DJ perovskites, Kanatzidis et al. replaced the monoammonium cations in RP, by two diammonium piperidine based cations, where an aminomethyl (-CH₂NH₃) group was attached to meta- (3AMP) and para-(4AMP) positions of piperidine nitrogen.[101] The fabricated PSCs with different inorganic layer thickness ($n = 3,4$) and measured a high PCE of 7.32% with 3AMPMA₃Pb₄I₁₃ ($n = 4$) where the 4AMPMA₃Pb₄I₁₃ ($n = 4$) achieved only 4.24%. The higher PCE of 3AMP based DJ-PSC was attributed to its lower band gap as compared to 4AMP. The systematic crystallographic and theoretical experiments showed the higher equatorial I-Pb-I bond angle lowered the band gap.

Later, the perovskite cage was modified by replacing 25% of MA by FA, and the corresponding device in FTO: PEDOT:3AMP(MA_{0.75}FA_{0.25})₃Pb₄I₁₃:C₆₀/BCP:Ag configuration gave a PCE of 12.04% PCE. The crystallographic studies revealed that the improved equatorial I-Pb-I bond angle (173.8°) reduced the band gap (1.18 eV) and the A-site compositional engineering led to preferentially oriented vertical growth and there by improved the charge carrier transportation. The unencapsulated champion PSCs showed better stability than of 3D analogue (MA_{0.75}FA_{0.25}PbI₃) as well as the RP perovskites based PSCs with BA counterpart.[100] Further, Lee and his co-workers introduced compositional engineering at A' site (spacer cation) and the corresponding PDAMA₃Pb₄I₁₃ (PDA- propane-1,3-diammonium) based DJ-PSC showed an enhanced

PCE of 13% with negligible hysteresis.[102] The smaller PDA cation based DJ-perovskites showed improved photocarrier lifetime and carrier mobilities than the control BA based RP perovskites indicating inhibited recombination and efficient charge transport between the inorganic wells. Thus, fabricated *p-i-n* type PSCs with PDA demonstrated exceptional stability over the reference device even under harsh conditions. Li et al. improved the PCE to 13.3% and compared the PDA with PA counterpart.[43] The unencapsulated device retained 95% of initial performance after 4000 hours of storage at ambient air (40-70% RH), 168 hours of thermal stress (85°C, 85% RH) and 3000 hours of light illumination. The device performance was further improved to 17.91 by employing BDA (butane-1,3-diammonium) spacer cation.[103] The effect of QW barrier length was demonstrated by Huang, where BDA and PDA favored better charge transport than the longer spacer cations. Recently, Shi and co-workers reported a new asymmetric alkyl spacer based DJ-PSC with a PCE >15%.[104] The DMAPA barrier depicted with sequential transfer of photocarriers from $n=1$ phase to other phases with high n values. The improved phase distribution and low defect density contributed to a hysteresis free PSCs with improved environmental stability. The enhanced PCE and stability of DJ over RP perovskites is mainly attributed to the removal of van der Waals gap and the strengthening of hydrogen bond by diamines.

Aromatic Spacer cations: It was established from RP perovskites, that the aromatic spacer cations can improve the dielectric constant of interlayer space, rigidity of cation and delocalization of positive charge on the aromatic ring, which would affect in favor of device performance by improving the charge transportation. Graetzel et.al. employed PDMA (1,4-phenylenedimethan ammonium) along with FA cation for the first time in DJ perovskites with $n = 1-4$.[105] The PDMAFA₂Pb₃I₁₀ based mesoporous device displayed a decent PCE of 7.11% without any additives. PDAMA improved the performance and stability of device compared to its 3D analogue. Later, Li et al. prepared aromatic 3AMPY based DJ perovskites and the champion device exhibited PCE of 9.20% with a short-circuit current density of 14.34 mA/cm², which was higher than the aliphatic analogue 3AMP based one with a PCE of 6.89% and J_{sc} of 9.11 mA/cm².[106] The higher dielectric constant of 3AMPY (~3) over the 3AMP (~2) owing to the more delocalized π -electron system, reduces the dielectric mismatch between the inorganic cage and the organic spacer. The lower dielectric confinement was attributed to the improved device performance. In recent report, a thiophene based spacer cation was employed in DJ-PSC by Liu. Although, ThDMA (2,5-thiophenedimethyl ammonium) based DJ perovskites

with $n = 5$ gave lower PCE, a DMSO assisted fabrication yielded a record PCE of 15.75% with an V_{oc} of 1.07 V, J_{sc} of 19.55 mA/cm² and FF of 75.46% in a *p-i-n* device architecture.[107] The DMSO assisted (ThDMA)MA₄Pb₅I₁₆ gave reduced band gap due to improved crystallinity. The larger and vertically oriented crystallites were evidenced from GIWAXS analysis. Along with the higher average decay time, DMSO interaction suppressed the trap assisted recombination losses in favor of enhanced performance. Moreover, the unencapsulated champion device showed improved environmental stability. Although DJ perovskites has demonstrated promising potential for PV application with exceptional stability and improved PCE, the design of new organic spacers as well as device engineering are paramount to boost their PV performance.

5.2 Mixed dimensional layered/3D perovskites for solar cells:

The mixed dimensional layered/3D perovskites have come to the light as the emerging materials for PSCs (Figure 6a). These mixed dimensional perovskites exhibit tuneable optical properties and most significantly renders better stability to the fabricated PSCs under ambient conditions.[27, 36] This layered/3D mixed dimensional perovskites appears to be a promising candidate to balance the equilibrium between the device performance and long-term operational stability of the PSCs.

Fig. 8 (a) Schematic illustration of the randomly inserted bulky organic layer into the 3D perovskite. (b) Top view SEM image of control 3D perovskite and layered 3D perovskite on glass/SnO₂ substrate. Reproduced with permission figure (a-b) from ref. [124] (c) J - V curve of pure 3D and NMA-layered/3D based solar cells. Reproduced with permission from ref. [132] (d) GIWAXS pattern of PEA-2D and iso-BA-2D perovskite films. Reproduced with permission from ref. [134]

5.2.1 Layered/3D mixed perovskite:

Owing to their large band gaps and restricted charge transport barrier in the pure layered perovskite, they fail to offer higher device performances in the PSCs. However, when the large organic cations of the layered perovskites are incorporated to replace the compact amount of the organic cations in the precursor solution of the 3D perovskites, the optoelectronic behaviour is altered significantly without affecting the band properties and rendered in improve device performances and stability, these are summarized in Table 3.[28]

Zhou et al incorporated a stable layered perovskite formed in-situ $(\text{PEI})_2\text{PbI}_4$ in small portion with $\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3$ that showed the slowing down of the crystal growth with uniform film morphology up to an optimized amount of layered perovskite doping. The best PCE of 15.2% was obtained with $(\text{MAPbI}_3)_{1-x}[(\text{PEI})_2\text{PbI}_4]_x$ at $x=2\%$. [108] The devices were highly reproducible and also showed better moisture stability than that of the control 3D based $(\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_3\text{PbI}_3)$ one. Gardener et al developed three different layered alkyldiammonium lead iodide perovskite and showed the synthesis and use of the materials in the PSCs. [109] Yang et al reported the use of guanidinium as an additive in MAPbI_3 to enhance the charge carrier lifetime with an increase V_{oc} of 1.12V and PCE $>17\%$ with reduced surface defects was obtained. [110] Nazeeruddin et al also reported the use of guanidinium cation into the MAPbI_3 crystal structure that yielded the overall PCE of 19% and stabilized device performance for 1000 h after continuous light illumination (Fig. 8e). [111] Later, they also demonstrated the multidimensional layered/3D perovskite $(\text{AVA}_2\text{PbI}_4)_{0.03}(\text{MAPbI}_3)_{0.97}$ on a $10\times 10\text{ cm}^2$ solar cell module to obtain a PCE of 11.2% with stability $> 10,000\text{h}$ under continuous illumination at 55°C . [112] Zhang et al reported a phase stable $\alpha\text{-CsPbI}_3$ with a layered perovskite component EDAPbI_4 that not only helped in phase stability but also enhances effective electron transfer by passivating the surface defects. [113] Snaith et al incorporated the butyl ammonium within the $\text{BA}_x(\text{FA}_{0.83}\text{Cs}_{0.17})_{1-x}\text{Pb}(\text{I}_{0.6}\text{Br}_{0.4})_3$ based lead halide perovskite that they found as a flakes to be scattered between the 3D perovskite grains, remarkably enhanced the crystallinity of the film, reduce nonradiative charge recombination and measured a PCE of 19.5% with cell sustained stability of 80% after 1000 h in air. [114] The incorporation of phenylethylammonium cation was demonstrated by Baillie and co-workers for the first time into a mixed perovskite $(\text{FAPbI}_3)_{0.85}(\text{MAPbBr}_3)_{0.15}$ that retained the moisture stability, enhancement in crystallinity with passivation of the grain boundaries. [115] Also, the incorporation of PEA^+ helped in the increase in V_{oc} of the PSCs and highest PCE of 14.3% was obtained. The phase stability of guanidinium incorporated into 3D perovskites lattices was demonstrated by Emsley et al and showed that the $\text{GUA}_x\text{MA}_{1-x}\text{PbI}_3$ component are stable for months with $x<40\text{ mol}\%$ with long charge carrier lifetimes measured by time resolved photoluminescence and improved PV performances. [116] Etgar and co-workers studied the influence of incorporation of barrier molecules and Cs on the layered/3D crystal structure and found that the spacer molecules did not appreciably improved the PV performances but helped in stability than the Cs and cyclo spacer-based molecule. [117]

They also proposed that the increase in number of distortions due to the size of the small Cs cation could accelerate the degradation process of the perovskites. Jiang et al introduced an amount of PEAI to a highly robust α -CsPbX₃ that suppressed the undesirable phase transition and reduce the film's trap state density.[118] The champion device with a PCE of 12.4% was obtained with improved performance longevity. A high quality stable FAPbI₃ with incorporation of phenyl ethyl ammonium iodide (PEAI) based perovskite in the precursor solution was demonstrated by Yang and co-workers that helped in the moisture resistibility and with notable charge separation stability of the device.[119] The reported PCE was c.a. 20.64 % with a V_{oc} of 1.13V. The large radius of layered cation phenmethylammonium (PEA) was incorporated in the CsPbI₃ structure by Liu et al that could modulate the phase transition temperature and enhance the perovskite phase stability at ambient temperature.[120] The incorporation of PEA⁺ effectively improved the film morphology and optoelectronic properties and achieved a PCE of 5.7% with negligible hysteresis. A RP/3D heterostructure based perovskite was demonstrated by Niu et al for-phase stability from α to δ phase in FAPbI₃ at room temperature.[121] A PCE as high as 20.63% was achieved along with a remarkable long-term stability up to 2880 h without encapsulation at ambient temperature was shown. Matsuo et al demonstrated an inverted type layered/3D FACsPbI₃ by employing the phenylethylamine (PEA) that exhibited higher stability and reproducibility with a PCE of 18.2%.[122] They also showed the device performance for *n-i-p* configuration with SnO₂ as the ETL layer that achieved a PCE of 20.2%. However, their reproducibility and stability were limited as compared to the inverted devices. They further explained that the improvement in performances might be due to strong interaction of the phenylethylamine (PEA) with the FACsPbI₃ through strong hydrogen bonding interaction at the grain boundaries that led to higher phase stability. A carbazole based organic cation with an alkyl spacer moiety with π -extended system was developed by Herckens and co-workers to form a multi-layered perovskite $\{(CA-C_4)_2MA_{n-1}Pb_nI_{3n-1}\}$. [123] This layered perovskite showed a PCE of 6.6 % with a higher moisture stability. It was also found that films of low-*n* carbazole containing perovskite showed higher photoconductivity and films with higher *n* (*n* = 40) contained higher charge carrier diffusion length. Zhou et al developed a highly efficient layered/3D perovskite by incorporating 2-thiophene methyl ammonium (ThMA) cations into FA/MA based 3D perovskites.[124] This incorporation led to an increase in grain size of the perovskite and enhancement in the charge mobility and charge carrier lifetime (Fig. 8b). The PCE measured was 21.49% with a high V_{oc} of 1.16 V, *FF* of c.a. 81%, that

retained moisture stability, 99% of its initial PCE was retained after encapsulated device for 1680 h under continuous light soaking. Ning et al. reported by incorporation of a secondary amine, dimethylamine (DMA) to partially replace the methylamine (MA) in the $MA_{1-x}DMA_xPbI_3$ structure to increase the crystal rigidity in the perovskite layer and reduction in the defect density between the perovskite/HTL interface layer.[125] The champion device showed a PCE of 21.6% with a V_{oc} of 1.11 V, J_{sc} of 23.5 and FF of ~82%. The improved operational stability of the perovskite was explained by the water repellent properties of the secondary amines that help retained 80% of the initial PCE when encapsulated device were kept for 800 h under continuous light illumination. Similarly, Wang et al introduced the n-butyl ammonium iodide (BAI) in a layered/3D layered structure and by doing so enhanced the PCE to 18 %, along with long-term device stability of $MAPbI_3$. [126] Another strategy to improve the efficiency and stability of the PSCs was introduced by Hao and co-workers by employing phenylethylammonium iodide (PEAI) and *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF) as the additives.[127] The strategy of using DMF with PEA I was to assist the cation of layered perovskite penetrate into the 3D perovskite layer in order to form the bilayer type layer/3D perovskite. A PCE as high as 22.18% was obtained and the effective charge transport and low charge recombination adds on to the factor of improved PV performances. Pham et al developed a new phenomenon of doping the mixed cation formamidinium-cesium lead triiodide ($FA_{0.83}Cs_{0.17}PbI_3$) perovskite with different concentration of guanidinium (Gu^+) cations to control the hysteresis and performance.[128] Their results suggests that the Gu^+ cations substitute the FA^+ cations in the perovskite lattice that altered the optoelectronic properties and the 2% Gu^+ doped device gave improved device performance (>17 %) and negligible hysteresis. The incorporation of hydrophilic alkylammonium salts often affects the humidity and stability of the perovskite, devices based on longer alkylammonium salts show better hydrophobicity however the overall PCE decreases. Thus to, maintain the hydrophobic character and better device performance, Dai and co-workers employed two hydrophobic short chain alkylammonium salts with halogen functional groups 2-chloroethylamine (CEA^+) and 2-bromoethylamine (BEA^+) cations with 3D perovskite ($Cs_{0.1}FA_{0.9}Pb(I_{0.9}Br_{0.1})_3$).[129] The introduction of these short hydrophobic alkylammonium groups (5% $CEA-Cl$) induce positive effect in the device performance with maximum PCE of 20.08% with superior moisture resistant retaining 92% of the initial PCE when the devices were aged at a relative humidity of 55% for 2400 h. Nazeeruddin et al introduced a new 'A' cation 2-chloroethylamine ($CIEA$) into the

MAPbI₃ lattice, they find 5% CIEA incorporation led to the retention of high thermal stability.[130] Wu et al has incorporated large guanidinium cations (GUA⁺) into mixed 3D perovskite lattice that was found to have less defects, lower the non-radiative charge recombination and lower trap density.[131] It yielded boosted V_{oc} from 1.11 V to 1.19 V and an impressive PCE of 21%. The increase in V_{oc} on the incorporation of bulky amine cation was also demonstrated by McLachlan.[132] They employed 1-naphthylmethylamine (NMA) in MAPbI₃, to enhance the V_{oc} from 1.06 V to 1.16 V in inverted *p-i-n* type planar architecture and the PCE up to 20.1% (Fig. 8c). Graetzel and co-workers introduced the use of guaninium (G) to stabilize the α -FAPbI₃ phase.[133] A PCE of 16.04% was achieved with a V_{oc} of 1.08 V, J_{sc} of 22.08 mAcm⁻² and FF of 67%. Zuo and co-workers demonstrated a quasi-layered/3D perovskite and measured a PCE of 16%. They also performed the synchrotron-based grazing incidence wide angle X-ray scattering (GIWAXS) to find the crystal orientation in the film (Fig. 8d).[134] These results give a distinct idea about the outstanding performances of layered perovskite and pave ways for improving the efficiency and stability of layered/3D multidimensional perovskites.

Table 3: Layered/3D perovskites absorber for perovskite solar cells

Perovskite	Device configuration	PCE (%)	Stability
(MAPbI ₃) _{0.98} [(PEI) ₂ PbI ₄] _{0.02}	<i>p-i-n</i>	15.2	16% loss in PCE after 14 th day, dark, 50% relative humidity
(AVA ₂ PbI ₄) _{0.03} (MAPbI ₃) _{0.97}	<i>n-i-p</i>	11.2	No PCE loss after 10000 h under continuous illumination
BA _{0.09} (FA _{0.83} Cs _{0.17}) _{0.91} Pb(I _{0.6} Br _{0.4}) ₃	<i>n-i-p</i>	17.2	80% PCE after 1000 h, air, dark
PEA ₂ Cs _{n-1} Pb _n X _{3n-1} (n=40)	<i>n-i-p</i>	11.3	93% of initial PCE after 40 days storage
MA _{0.86} Gua _{0.14} PbI ₃	<i>n-i-p</i>	20.15	Gradual stabilization observed when kept under illumination for 1000 h at 60 °C
Cs _{0.9} PEA _{0.1} PbI ₃	<i>n-i-p</i>	5.7	75% of initial PCE after 95 h, air

CsPbI ₃ .0.25EDAPbI ₄	<i>n-i-p</i>	11.8	10% initial PCE, dark, 30 days
MA _{0.89} DMA _{0.11} PbI ₃	<i>p-i-n</i>	21.6	80% of initial PCE, light, 800 h
(CEA ₂ PbX ₄) _{0.05} [(Cs _{0.1} FA _{0.9})Pb(I _{0.9} Br _{0.1}) ₃] _{0.95}	<i>n-i-p</i>	20.08	90% of initial PCE, 50% RH, 2400 h
(PEA ₂ PbI ₄) _{0.017} (MAPbI ₃)	<i>n-i-p</i>	19.84	96% of PCE retained after 100 h, dark
MA _{0.97} CIEA _{0.03} PbI ₃	<i>n-i-p</i>	18.28	N/A
(BzDA)(Cs _{0.05} MA _{0.15} FA _{0.8}) ₉ Pb ₁₀ (I _{0.93} Br _{0.07}) ₃₁	<i>n-i-p</i>	15.6	80% PCE after 84 h
CA ₂ MA ₃₉ Pb ₄₀ I ₁₂₁ (n=40)	<i>n-i-p</i>	6.6	59% of PCE after 264 h, dark, 77% RH
Gua _{0.1} [(Cs _{0.1} (FA _{0.83} MA _{0.17}) _{0.9}) _{0.9} Pb(I _{0.83} Br _{0.17}) ₃]	<i>n-i-p</i>	21.12	N/A
NMA-MAPbI ₃	<i>p-i-n</i>	20.1	N/A
G ₂ FA _{n-1} Pb _n I _{3n-1}	<i>n-i-p</i>	16.04	N/A
(Da ₂ PbI ₄) _{0.05} (MAPbI ₃)	<i>n-i-p</i>	19.05	80% of PCE after 60 days, dark

Fig. 9 (a) Schematic representation of the methods used to incorporate fluorine based layered perovskite on top of 3D perovskite. Reproduced with permission from ref. [137] (b) Top view SEM images and XRD patterns of control and SSG-G films. Reproduced with permission from ref. [146] (c) $J-V$ curve of pure 3D and 3D/LP (C_4Br , C_6Br , C_8Br) based solar cells. (d) TRPL trace of 3D and 3D/LP (C_4Br , C_6Br , C_8Br) based quartz films. Reproduced with permission figure (c-d) from ref. [147] (e) stability measurement of power conversion efficiency of the control and target device, stored under dark with controlled humidity and measured in ambient atmosphere. Reproduced with permission from ref. [148] (f) XRD pattern of 3D and three-layered/3D perovskites. Reproduced with permission from ref. [157]

5.2.2. Modification of 3D interfaces by employing layered perovskites:

The interface of 3D perovskite absorber is found to be modified by presence of layered perovskite or bulky organic halides as an interfacial layer between the perovskite/HTL interfaces. These interlayer helps in reducing the surface defects, lower trap state densities and improve the charge carrier dynamics in the perovskite layer.[135-136] It also act as moisture resistance layer and preserves the stability of the perovskite absorber due to its hydrophobic nature.[137] A thin layer of bulky cation is usually spin coated atop of the 3D perovskite layer using solvents like isopropanol (IPA) or chloroform (CHCl_3) and subject to annealing at a required temperature ($100\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) that enables the cation exchange reaction between the layered and 3D perovskite structure, this helps in the formation of layered perovskite with enhanced interfacial charge collection. The accumulation of hydrophobic tertiary and quaternary alkyl ammonium cations on the perovskite surfaces were demonstrated by Yang and co-workers.[138] The surface engineering not only endowed moisture stability but also improves PV performances. Shi et al demonstrated layered/3D perovskite hybrids ($\text{CA}_2\text{PbI}_4/\text{MAPbI}_x\text{Cl}_{3-x}$) as light absorbers that showed comparatively higher moisture stability.[139] Mathews and co-workers demonstrated the use of two different alkyl ammonium cations butylammonium iodide and octylammonium iodide that diffuse into the surface of 3D perovskite and form a layered/3D perovskite hybrid that enhances the water repellent properties of the perovskite layer.[136] Similarly, Nazeeruddin and co-workers showed the employment of phenylethylammonium iodide (PEAI) as a very thin layer atop of 3D mixed halide perovskite $\text{Cs}_{0.1}\text{FA}_{0.74}\text{MA}_{0.13}\text{PbI}_{2.48}\text{Br}_{0.39}$ to provide long term stability.[140] In another work they demonstrated the synthesis and use of a fluoros cation $(\text{CF}_3)_3\text{CO}(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{NH}_3^+$ in the form of iodide salts on the top of two different $\text{MA}_{0.9}\text{FA}_{0.1}\text{PbI}_3$ and $\text{Cs}_{0.1}\text{FA}_{0.74}\text{MA}_{0.13}\text{PbI}_{2.48}\text{Br}_{0.39}$ (Fig. 7a).[137] The fluoros based cation serve as a water proof sheath and preserved the perovskite layer with competitive stability, improved interface with HTL and a V_{oc} of 1.12 V with 20% PCE. Park and co-workers introduced the use of 5-ammonium valeric acid iodide salt (5-AVAI) as an ultrathin layer over the 3D perovskite.[141] This interface layer reduced the hysteresis and enhance the charge extraction property along with moisture and photo stability along with improved PV performances. The introduction of octylammonium (OA) iodide was demonstrated by Seok et al and deposited atop of MAPbI_3 , it gave improved device performances and stability towards heat, light and humidity.[142] Wang and co-workers rationally designed

the capping of mixed halide perovskite with PEA_2PbI_4 that induced larger Fermi-level splitting to reduced non-radiative charge recombination and lower the decrease in voltage loss along with higher stability in humid environment.[143] Layered capping of all inorganic CsPbI_3 perovskite with phenylethylamine cation (PEA^+) was presented by Zhao and co-workers to improve the phase stability and moisture resistance, a PCE of 13.5% was measured.[144] They also noted that the post treatment of phenyltrimethylammonium bromide (PTABr) on $\alpha\text{-CsPbI}_3$ improve the phase stability and moisture tolerance and gave reproducible device performance with PCE of 17.06%.[145] Zhu and co-workers employed the modification of surface of the perovskite that could widen the band gap to effectively achieve a higher V_{oc} by introducing guanidinium bromide. The morphology of the grain size of the control and SSG-G modified perovskite was performed through scanning electron microscope (SEM) (Fig. **9b**).[146] The authors achieve a V_{oc} of 1.21 V with a champion PCE of 21.51%. Bawendi et al reported a unique strategy of combining 2D precursor (linear alkyl ammonium bromide) and solvent (chloroform) to form a thin film atop of 3D perovskite that could help in defect passivation, allows moisture resistance and improve the PV performances mainly in terms of V_{oc} and longer charge carrier lifetime (Fig. **9c,d**).[147] This strategy helped them to achieve a PCE of 23.4% with V_{oc} of 1.16 V, J_{sc} of 24.5 mA/cm^2 and FF of 82.3%. Gao and co-workers further employed the use fluorinated aromatic cation of 2-(4-fluorophenyl)ethyl ammonium iodide (FPEAI) capped over the 3D perovskite that enhances the environmental stability from moisture and degradation together with improved PV performances (Fig. **9e**).[148] The introduction of three different ammonium salts ethylammonium iodide (EAI), imidazolium iodide (IAI) and guanidinium iodide (GuaI) were put forward by Gratezel and co-workers as the surface passivating agents or buffer layers.[149] These layers showed a significant enhancement in the V_{oc} , reduction in hysteresis, device stability with PCE as high as 22.3% (EAI), 22.1 % (IAI) and 21.0% (GuaI) respectively. They also demonstrated successful use of pentafluorophenyl ethylamine (FPEA) as an ultrathin layer atop of the 3D perovskite (FAPbI_3) that stabilises the phase transformation and adds hydrophobic behaviour to the layer. Another method developed by Lin et al to form layered/3D perovskite was by introducing less amount of dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) into BAI in chlorobenzene to allow the cation conversion process on the inorganic CsPbI_2Br perovskite.[150] This method facilitates the hole extraction phenomenon and thereby increases the J_{sc} of the device. Liu and co-workers demonstrated the layered/3D perovskite by employing 4-fluorophenethylamine iodide in

isopropanol atop of the FAPbI_3 perovskite to influences the charge transport/ extraction and PV performances.[151] Nogueira et al demonstrated the layered/3D perovskite by employing various aliphatic long chain alkylammonium chloride atop of MAPbI_3 and noted enhance charge carrier lifetime and moisture tolerance properties.[152] Seok and co-workers employed the similar method of post treatment of various alkyl ammonium salts over $(\text{FAPbI}_3)_{0.95}(\text{MAPbBr}_3)_{0.05}$ and by optimizing their results the best PCE of 22.9% and stability towards humidity was noted.[153] Wang et al too employed choline iodide (CHI) as a post treatment material atop of the $\beta\text{-CsPbI}_3$ that helped passivating the surface trap states and aligned the energy level at the interfaces.[154] Gracini et.al. studied the layered/3D interfaces that was revealed to be dynamic in nature.[155] They employed thiophene alkyl ammonium iodide cations over the 3D perovskite which helped to protect from degradation in the ambient air and improved the device performance upon aging. Another strategy to use hexylammonium iodide (HAI) to passivate the surface defects on the 3D perovskite layer was made by Shi et.al., and resulted in enhance charge carrier lifetime and also minimizes the interfacial charge recombination process.[156] A PCE of 20.62% was obtained along with long term stability of the PSCs against heat and humidity. Gao et al demonstrated the use of mono-fluorinated phenylethylammonium iodides and varied the position of substituents (*m*-FPEAI, *o*-FPEAI, *p*-FPEAI) with a distinctive X-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern on the surface of triple cations based mixed perovskite (Fig. 9f).[157] Depending on the positions, these ammonium salts improves the trap state defects, charge carrier concentration, reduces the non-radiative recombination and also improve the stability of the PSCs. Ma and co-workers developed the use of *N,N'*-dimethylethylene-1,2-diammonium iodide (DMEDAI₂) atop of MAPbI_3 to improve the optical and performances of the PSCs.[158] They achieved a PCE of 20.2% with a V_{oc} of 1.14 V, J_{sc} of 22.57 mA/cm^2 and fill factor FF of 78% along with improve stability. Another approach of using the fluorinated phenylethylammonium iodide (FPEAI) on the Cs-based mixed halide perovskite was reported by Nazeeruddin et.al. to passivate the defect states and improve the device stability.[159] Paetzold et al employed the layered/3D heterostructure in a 4T tandem configuration with c-Si and CIGS bottom solar cells to reduce the non-radiative charge recombination and improve V_{oc} and PCE of 25.7% (perovskites/c-Si) and 25.0% (perovskites/CIGS) respectively was recorded.[160] White and co-workers made the double sided passivation of the 3D perovskite with *n*-butylammonium iodide and achieved a remarkable PCE of 22.60% with an V_{oc} of 1.2 V.[161] Investigations on the interfacial layered perovskites atop of 3D

perovskites is vital, to provide promising pathway towards photo-chemical stability and remarkable device performances as compared to the 3D counterpart. Research efforts are being laid to tune the optical band gap and improving the charge transport properties to overcome the challenge addressed. Important reports on interfacial modification of layered/3D multidimensional perovskites are represented in Table 4.

Table 4: Interface layered/3D multidimensional perovskites

Perovskite	Device configuration	PCE (%)	Stability
CAI/MAPbI _x Cl _{3-x}	<i>p-i-n</i>	13.86	50% retain in PCE after 220 h, dark, 50% relative humidity
AX/CsPbI ₃	<i>n-i-p</i>	13.4	N/A
BAI/ Cs _{0.05} (MA _{0.17} FA _{0.83}) _{0.91} Pb(I _{0.83} Br _{0.17}) ₃	<i>n-i-p</i>	15.74	86% PCE after 100 h, dark, RH > 50 %
A43/Cs _{0.1} FA _{0.74} MA _{0.13} PbI _{2.48} Br _{0.39}	<i>n-i-p</i>	20.13	N/A
PEAI/Cs _{0.1} FA _{0.74} MA _{0.13} PbI _{2.48} Br _{0.39}	<i>n-i-p</i>	20.15	85% of initial PCE, 800 h 50 °C
5-AVA/(FAPbI ₃) _{0.88} (CsPbBr ₃) _{0.12}	<i>n-i-p</i>	16.75	98% of initial PCE after 63 days, 10% RH, dark
OA/MAPbI ₃	<i>n-i-p</i>	20.6	70% initial PCE, dark, 75 h
PEAI/Cs _{0.05} (MA _{0.17} FA _{0.83}) _{0.91} Pb(I _{0.83} Br _{0.17}) ₃	<i>n-i-p</i>	18.51	90% of initial PCE, dark, 1000 h
PEAI/CsPbI ₃	<i>n-i-p</i>	13.5	
PTABr/CsPbI ₃	<i>n-i-p</i>	17.06	91% of PCE retained after 500 h, light, N ₂
SSG-G/(FA _{0.95} PbI _{2.95}) _{0.85} (MAPbPr ₃) _{0.15}	<i>p-i-n</i>	20.91	95% of PCE retained after 500 h at 85 °C
2-TEAI/[(FAPbI ₃) _{0.87} (MAPbBr ₃) _{0.13}] _{0.92} (CsPbI ₃) _{0.08}	<i>n-i-p</i>	19.42	90% PCE after 1000 h, dark
F5PEAI/Cs _{0.04} FA _{0.92} MA _{0.04} PbI ₃	<i>n-i-p</i>	22.16	90% of initial PCE, dark, 1000 h, 40 % RH
FPEAI/ Cs _{0.1} (MA _{0.17} FA _{0.83})Pb(I _{0.83} Br _{0.17}) ₃	<i>n-i-p</i>	20.54	99% of PCE after 864 h, dark, 10-30% RH
C ₆ Br/(FAPbI ₃) _{0.92} (MAPbBr ₃) _{0.08}	<i>n-i-p</i>	23.4	85% of PCE after 500 h
EAI/(FA _{0.9} Cs _{0.07} MA _{0.03} Pb(I _{0.92} Br _{0.08}) ₃	<i>n-i-p</i>	22.3	95% of PCE after 550 h

BAI/CsPbI ₂ Br	<i>n-i-p</i>	14.5	80% of PCE after 25 days, dark
PEAI/(FAPbI ₃) _{0.85} (MAPbBr ₃) _{0.15}	<i>n-i-p</i>	24.66	90% of initial PCE, 600 h
PEAI-FAI/FAPbI ₃	<i>n-i-p</i>	21.15	52% of PCE after 60 days, dark
BABr/ Cs _{0.17} FA _{0.83} Pb(I _{0.6} Br _{0.4}) ₃	<i>n-i-p</i>	19.8	N/A
HTAB/(FAPbI ₃) _{0.55} (MAPbBr ₃) _{0.05}	<i>n-i-p</i>	23.3	95% of initial PCE, 1370 h
pFPEAI/Cs _{0.05} FA _{0.79} MA _{0.16} Pb(I _{2.49} Br _{0.51})	<i>n-i-p</i>	19.55	99% of initial PCE, 60 days, dark
AzPbI ₃ / Cs _{0.05} MA _{0.1} FA _{0.85} PbI _{2.7} Br _{0.3}	<i>n-i-p</i>	22	85% of initial PCE, 1000 h at 52 °C, N ₂
DMEDAI ₂ /MAPbI ₃	<i>n-i-p</i>	20.2	73.7% of initial PCE, 30 days, air
FPEAI/(FAPbI ₃) _{0.77} (MAPbBr ₃) _{0.14} (CsPbI ₃) _{0.09}	<i>n-i-p</i>	18.03	90% of initial PCE, 400 h

5.3. Lead free layered/3D based perovskite solar cells

Lead (Pb) has been employed as the important divalent cation in the perovskite structure owing to its high-performance in PSCs. However, lead tends to evolve out of the perovskite crystal structure as a degradation product when exposed to moisture or humidity and its toxic impact on the environment has been a subject of concern.[162-163] Furthermore, lead presence does not allow the recycling process that is feasible with other PV technologies like CIGS and CdTe. Researchers, has explored new alternatives to replace Pb²⁺ with Sn²⁺, Ge²⁺ and Bi³⁺, however they are governed by lower PCE and poor stability. Recently, many reports have been developed where the Pb²⁺ was replaced by Sn²⁺ to demonstrate the lead free layered/3D PSCs. However, the usage of tin instead of lead is under constant observation as Sn²⁺ valence state is unstable that could readily get oxidised to Sn⁴⁺, in contrast the introduction of tin could narrow the band gap when compared to lead. Table 5 represents lead free layered perovskites and fabricated devices thereof.

Fig. 10 (a) Schematic representation of FASnI_3 , $(\text{PEA})_2\text{SnI}_4$ and mixed FA-PEA tin perovskite (PEA % mole percentage of PEA). Reproduced with permission from ref. [166] (b) $J-V$ curve of (PEA-FA) SnI_3 Reproduced with permission from ref. [170] (c) SEM images of $\text{PEA}_2\text{MA}_3\text{SnI}_{13}$ (top surface view, bottom-cross section view). Reproduced with permission from ref. [165] (d) Steady state PL spectra of control and layered/3d perovskites. Reproduced with permission from ref. [169] (e) Band alignment diagram, $J-V$ curves and stability for $(4\text{AMP})(\text{FA})_3\text{Sn}_4\text{I}_{13}$ ($n = 4$) Reproduced with permission from ref. [168] The American Chemical Society, Copyright 2018.

Table 5: Lead free layered perovskites

Perovskite	Device configuration	PCE (%)	Stability
$(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA})_{n-1}\text{Sn}_n\text{I}_{3n+1}$, ($n = 4$)	<i>n-i-p</i>	2.53	90% of initial PCE after 30 days
$(\text{PEA})_2(\text{FA})_{n-1}\text{Sn}_n\text{I}_{3n-1}$ ($n = 9$)	<i>p-i-n</i>	5.98	96% of initial PCE after 100 h, dark
$(\text{PEA})_2(\text{FA})_{n-1}\text{Sn}_n\text{I}_{3n-1}$ ($n = 50$)	<i>p-i-n</i>	9	59% of initial PCE after 100 h, 20% RH, dark
$(4\text{AMP})(\text{FA})_3\text{Sn}_4\text{I}_{13}$	<i>n-i-p</i>	4.22	9% decay in initial PCE at 45 °C for 100 h
$(\text{BA}_{0.5}\text{PEA}_{0.5})_2\text{FA}_3\text{Sn}_4\text{I}_{13}$ ($n = 4$)	<i>p-i-n</i>	8.82	59% PCE after 1 week, dark
Bn_2SnI_4	<i>n-i-p</i>	2.3	N/A
pPDACuBr ₄	-	-	Stable up to 1200 h in air
$\text{FASnI}_3:\text{PEACl}$	<i>p-i-n</i>	9.1	1500 h storage

Kanatzidis et al. were the first to demonstrate the lead-free perovskite[164] and were to explain the Ruddlesden-Popper $(\text{BA})_2(\text{MA})_{n-1}\text{Sn}_n\text{I}_{3n+1}$ perovskite ($n = 1 - 5$) as the low dimensional lead-free perovskites.[165] To protect the oxidation Sn^{2+} to Sn^{4+} , they used triethylphosphine (TEP) as an antioxidant which improves the perovskite film microstructure and thus, device performance (Fig. 10c). Inclusion of the bulky cations resulted in lowering the optical band gap from 1.80 eV ($n = 1$) to 1.20 eV ($n = \infty$), whereas for PSCs, $n = 3, 4$ were chosen. Tin based layered PSCs were obtained with PCE of 1.94% ($n = 3$) and 2.5% ($n = 4$) in an inverted planar configuration. The encapsulated devices retained 90% of initial PCE up to 1 months and reduced to 50% after four months. Liao at al reported the incorporation of phenylethylammonium (PEA) as an interlayer by increasing the thickness to $n = 9$ $(\text{PEA})_2(\text{FA})_8\text{Sn}_9\text{I}_{28}$ which produced much better stable device as compared to FASnI_3 . A schematic representation is shown in (Fig. 10a).[166] A PCE of 5.94% with a V_{oc} of 0.59V was obtained. A reproducible tin based layered perovskite was demonstrated by Shao et al by mixing a small amount of layered tin perovskite into a small amount of 3D tin perovskite to form $\text{PEA}_2\text{FA}_{49}\text{Sn}_{50}\text{I}_{151}$, this resulted in a remarkable PCE of 9%.[167] A lead free Dion-Jacobson tin (II) based perovskite $(4\text{AMP})(\text{FA})_3\text{Sn}_4\text{I}_{13}$ was demonstrated by Padture and co-workers and a PCE of 4.22% was reported (Fig. 10e).[168] Loi and co-workers incorporated ethylammonium iodide (EAI) to form EA_x layered/3D perovskite (layered= $(\text{PEA})_2\text{FASn}_2\text{I}_7$, 3D= FASnI_3) that improved the crystallinity of the perovskite film, reduced the trap state defects and

exhibited a PCE of 8.4%. The steady state studies shows lower non-radiative trap assisted recombination losses of charge carriers (Fig. **10d**).^[169] Wu et al demonstrated the incorporation of alkylammonium iodide cation (PEA⁺) in a tin based lead free perovskite and achieved a PCE of 6.98% (Fig. **10b**).^[170] Nazeeruddin and co-workers developed a layered perovskites based on tin with benzimidazolium Bn₂SnI₄ and a PCE of 2.3% was measured that also showed promising stability towards moisture.^[171] While Zeng and co-workers demonstrated a series of lead-free layered hybrid PSCs with diammonium (DA) cations (DA)(FA)_{n-1}Sn_nX_{3n+1} ($n = 1 - 4$) that showed improved charge carrier mobilities that may yield high PV performances and stability of PSCs.^[172]

Conclusion and outlook:

The current decade has witnessed a breakthrough in the advancement of perovskite solar cells research. 3D-perovskites has emerged as one of the finest candidates with promising photovoltaic performances, however it lacks behind in addressing the aspects required for successful commercialization. The plausible reason is its low stability and structural changes in the perovskite lattice. Layered perovskites are potentially attractive to overcome the disadvantages of 3D perovskites possess, owing to its higher stability and heterogeneity in elemental changes, that can help in maintaining the performances. The long aromatic or aliphatic organic cations induce structural flexibilities and intriguing electro-optical properties to imply in PV applications. However, challenges dealing with balancing the trade of between high-performance device and stability is yet to be tackle. Layered perovskites with large organic cations can have higher dielectric constant to facilitate improved charge transport, alignment of the energy level at the interfaces. By selective device architect and optimal microstructure an interface between the layered and the 3D framework for efficient transport of photogenerated charge carriers to the selective contacts can be elucidated. Theoretical simulations can help us to investigate the interfacial electronic structure, charge transfer dynamics and to understand the intrinsic light, heat and moisture stability in the layered hybrid perovskite-based absorbers for fast screening of materials. Development of hole selective contacts that can minimize the energy gap mismatch with that of the layered hybrid perovskite and has high carrier density will add value to the overall performance. Compositional engineering of large cations tailored with π - π stacking and hydrogen bonding can improve the charge transport properties in the lower dimensional perovskites. The understanding of the pure phase of layered perovskites, crystallographic orientations, charge transport phenomenon along

the in-plane and out-of-plane directions, to improve the photoluminescence quantum yield in the layered perovskite is vital to fabricate efficient solar cells. The placement of layered perovskite atop of 3D hybrid perovskite to form multidimensional perovskite adds to further improve the stability and performance of the devices. The understanding of the physio-chemical and electrical properties behind the layered perovskites can engrave its potential further as future wide band gap tuneable semiconductor for optoelectronic applications including solar cells, light emitting diodes, spintronic or heterogeneous photo-catalysis reactions.

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Conflict of interest statement

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest.

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